

PREDICTION OF RESIDUAL COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF IMPACT-DAMAGED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

An analytical model for the prediction of the compression-after-impact strength of composite laminates is developed. In this model, a sublaminar buckling approach is employed for determining the degradation of mechanical properties in the damaged region. The impact damage is then simulated as a soft inclusion and the stress redistribution is determined using the complex potential method. The point stress criterion is used to predict the compression-after-impact strength. The results of two test cases are compared with experimental data and good agreements are obtained which verify the accuracy of the predictions.

Keywords: Impact damage, compression-after-impact strength, carbon fibre reinforced composites, delamination and sublaminar buckling.

1. INTRODUCTION

The application of carbon fibre reinforced composites in primary aircraft structures requires the consideration of damage tolerance during the design phase. Impact loading is known to cause extensive internal delaminations and matrix cracking in composite structures. Since composites, in general, are not damage tolerant, impact damage can significantly degrade the compressive strength of composite laminates¹. Therefore the compression-after-impact behaviour of laminates is one of the major concerns in the design of primary composite structures. Considerable attention has recently been drawn to problems relating to the prediction of compression-after-impact strength with most of the research using fracture mechanics and numerical procedures^{2,3}.

It has been determined that the strength reduction in damaged laminates is caused by an instability of sublaminae formed by internal delaminations under in-plane compressive loads^{4,5}. The buckling of sublaminae triggers unstable delamination growth which in turn leads to a premature failure of the laminate. In a collaborative program with de Havilland Inc. concerning the use of advanced composites in primary aircraft structures, an analytical model for the prediction of compression-after-impact strength of composite laminates has been developed, at the Structures and Materials Laboratory of the Institute for Aerospace Research, using a sublaminar buckling approach⁶. This model can be used as a design tool to evaluate impact damage tolerance of composites and has been incorporated into the Design Analysis System (DAS) developed at the Institute for Aerospace Research⁷.

The present paper describes the detailed procedures of using the analytical model for the prediction of compression-after-impact strength of composite laminates. Results of two test cases are presented and the model is verified by comparing with experimental data. Results from a parametric study are also presented which demonstrate the various capabilities of the model.

2. MODELLING APPROACH

The accuracy of prediction depends on a three dimensional nondestructive characterization of the impact damage. In this work, damage characterization was performed using the ultrasonic time-of-flight C-scan technique⁸. It has been found that the impact damage involves delaminations, fibre breakages and matrix cracks at various through-the-thickness locations with the largest delamination occurring close to the back surface and the in-plane shape of the damage detected by the C-scan technique is elliptical.

When the damaged laminate is under compression, the largest sublaminates near the back surface will buckle which is followed by the buckling of other sublaminates in the damaged region prior to the ultimate failure of the laminate. Based on this failure mechanism, the initial stage of the current model, shown in Fig. 1a, is to calculate the stress at which the largest sublaminates buckle⁵. Subsequent to buckling, the second stage as shown in Fig. 1b is to simulate the damaged region as a soft inclusion and to determine the material degradation using the sublaminates buckling criterion illustrated in Fig. 1c. Then the stress redistribution in the laminated plate is calculated using Lekhnitskii's complex potential method⁹. The stresses in the vicinity of the soft inclusion, after being corrected for finite width effects¹⁰, are used in conjunction with the point stress failure criterion¹¹ for the prediction of residual compressive strength. It is worth mentioning that other failure criteria such as the maximum stress, Tsai-Wu etc. can be used in the model for failure prediction.

2.1 Sublaminates Buckling Analysis

Assuming an elliptical sublaminates in a rectangular laminate under uniaxial compression, the stress at which the sublaminates buckle is calculated using Rayleigh-Ritz method. The essential damage parameters required for sublaminates buckling analysis are the thickness of the largest sublaminates caused by impact, the major and minor axes of the damage ellipse, a and b , and the inclined angle, θ , as shown in Fig. 1b. These parameters are determined by the damage characterization.

The present sublaminates buckling model employs a six-term shape function in the energy formulation

$$w = [1 - (\frac{x'}{a})^2 - (\frac{y'}{b})^2]^2 (c_1 + c_2 x' + c_3 y' + c_4 x' y' + c_5 x'^2 + c_6 y'^2) \quad (1)$$

where w denotes the buckling mode, x' and y' are the local coordinates, Fig. 1b, and c_1 to c_6 are the six constants to be determined by solving the derived buckling equation.

It is noted that this shape function includes the three linear terms in addition to the constant and quadratic terms so that the buckling model can deal with the cases where the material properties of the sublaminates are not symmetric with respect to x' and y' axes. Substitution of equation 1 into the Rayleigh-Ritz energy formulation yields a matrix eigenvalue equation

$$[[K] + \sigma_b H [K_g]] \{C\} = \{0\} \quad (2)$$

where the eigenvalue σ_b gives the buckling stress and the eigenvector $\{C\}$ consisting of the six constants in Equation 1 gives the buckling mode, H is the laminate thickness, and $[K]$ and $[K_g]$ are

a) Sublaminates buckling.

b) Soft inclusion simulation.

c) Calculation of reduced modulus

Figure 1. Simulation of impact damage in laminate.

the stiffness and geometric stiffness matrices of order 6×6, respectively, which are given in Ref. 5.

2.2 Reduced Moduli for Damaged Region

A procedure, illustrated in Fig. 1c, is used to determine the material degradation of the damaged region. In the current analysis, the laminated plate containing impact damage is assumed to exhibit linear stress-strain relationship until the largest sublaminates buckle when the critical stress, σ_B , is reached. After buckling, the load carried by the sublaminates becomes constant, as in Euler buckling. In the post-buckled state, the axial modulus of the damaged region is further reduced under increasing compressive strain. The reduction in axial modulus is caused by a load redistribution within the damaged region which triggers delamination growth and buckling of the second largest sublaminates. This process is repeated until all sublaminae in the damaged region buckle under the increasing strain. At this stage the entire damaged region becomes a soft inclusion. This is a critical stage as a slight increase in compressive strain will trigger unstable collapse of the laminated plate. Using a maximum strain criterion, the most critical reduced axial modulus, E^* , is defined as:

$$E^* = \sigma_B / \epsilon_o = E \sigma_B / \sigma_o = M_r E \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_o is the failure strain of the undamaged laminate, E is the axial modulus of undamaged laminate and $M_r = \sigma_B / \sigma_o$ is called the modulus retention ratio. The transverse and shear moduli for the soft inclusion are assumed to be reduced by the same ratio, while Poisson's ratio remains unchanged.

2.3 Stress Distribution in Laminate with Soft Inclusion

The laminated plate containing impact damage can now be simulated by a similar plate with a soft inclusion. In order to predict the residual compressive strength, σ_{RS} , the in-plane stresses in the vicinity of the soft inclusion must be determined. The complex potential method⁹ is adopted to calculate the in-plane stresses of a uniaxially loaded laminate with elliptical inclusion, as shown in Fig. 1b. All quantities considered are with respect to the local coordinate system $x'-y'$. Then the stress resultants in laminate are derived by a superposition approach which are expressed as functions of two complex potentials ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} N_{x'} &= N_{x'}^o + 2 \operatorname{Re} \left[\mu_1^2 \frac{d\phi_1(z_1)}{dz_1} + \mu_2^2 \frac{d\phi_2(z_2)}{dz_2} \right] \\ N_{y'} &= N_{y'}^o + 2 \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{d\phi_1(z_1)}{dz_1} + \frac{d\phi_2(z_2)}{dz_2} \right] \\ N_{x'y'} &= N_{x'y'}^o - 2 \operatorname{Re} \left[\mu_1 \frac{d\phi_1(z_1)}{dz_1} + \mu_2 \frac{d\phi_2(z_2)}{dz_2} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $N_{x'}^o$, $N_{y'}^o$, and $N_{x'y'}^o$ are the stress resultants in the undamaged laminate, the other part denotes the stress state in a notched laminate, μ_1 and μ_2 are the two different complex roots (with positive imaginary part) of the characteristic equation in $x'-y'$ system⁹, and z_k are the two coordinate variables defined as $z_k = x' + \mu_k y'$ ($k = 1, 2$).

The two complex potentials are related to the inclusion configuration and loading conditions which are derived as:

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_1 &= \frac{1}{2(\mu_1 - \mu_2)} [(A - N_{x'}^o)bi - (B - N_{y'}^o)\mu_2 a + (C - N_{x'y'}^o)(i\mu_2 b - a)] \frac{1}{\zeta_1} \\ \varphi_2 &= \frac{-1}{2(\mu_1 - \mu_2)} [(A - N_{x'}^o)bi - (B - N_{y'}^o)\mu_1 a + (C - N_{x'y'}^o)(i\mu_1 b - a)] \frac{1}{\zeta_2}\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

where $i^2 = -1$, and parameters ζ_1 and ζ_2 are:

$$\zeta_k = (z_k + \sqrt{z_k^2 - a^2 - \mu_k^2 b^2}) / (a - i\mu_k b), \quad k = 1, 2 \quad (6)$$

In addition, parameters A , B , and C in Equation 5 denote the two normal and one shear stress components in the inclusion with respect to $x'-y'$ system. These stress components along with the rotational constant ω are determined by a set of complex algebraic equations resulting from the boundary conditions between the laminate and inclusion, outlined in Ref. 6.

2.4 Finite Width Correction

It is noted that the theory outlined in the previous section for stress redistribution is based on an infinite width assumption. When the damage size is large compared to the actual finite laminate width, a finite width correction factor (*FWC*) is required which is defined as the ratio of the stress concentration in a finite width plate (K_I) to that of an infinite width plate (K_I^∞). Considering the effect of a soft inclusion, the *FWC* equation for an isotropic plate with an open hole is modified by incorporating an exponent which is a function of M_r :

$$FWC = \{ [2 + (1 - D/W)^3] / [3(1 - D/W)] \}^{(1 - M_r^N)^M} \quad (7)$$

where D is the generalized diameter of damage ellipse, W is the width of laminate, and M and N are two constants determine by finite element analysis as 2.56 and 0.722, respectively⁴.

2.5 Failure Prediction of Residual Compressive Strength

After determining the stress resultants in the damaged laminate, the residual compressive strength is predicted using the point stress criterion¹¹. For this purpose, the stresses are transformed into the quantities in the global system x - y and corrected for finite width effects. The point stress criterion hypothesizes that failure will occur when the stress at a characteristic length, d_o , away from the damage boundary reaches the undamaged strength, σ_o , of the laminate. Similar to a notched strength problem, the point to be considered is located close to the boundary of the ellipse where the y -coordinate is $\pm D/2$, see Fig. 1b.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Two test cases were calculated to verify the prediction model developed. In the first case, the residual compressive strength of IM7/8551-7 [45/0/-45/90]_{3s} laminates having circular impact damage was predicted. The width and thickness of the Laminate are $W = 0.1016 \text{ m}$ and $H = 0.00451 \text{ m}$, respectively. The material data are $E_1 = 139.24 \text{ GPa}$, $E_t = 9.375 \text{ GPa}$, $G = 4.50 \text{ GPa}$, and $\nu = 0.33$. The sublaminates are assumed to be three plies thick. The characteristic length, d_o , was determined to be 0.000246 m based on a curve fitting of the test data reported in Ref. 4. The predicted strength ratios, which are defined as the ratio of the compressive strength of the damaged laminate to that of

the undamaged laminate, are plotted against various damage diameters in Fig. 2. Comparison between predictions and experimental data⁴ shows good agreement.

Figure 2. Residual strength of IM7/8551-7 [45/0/-45/90]_{3s} laminates with circular impact damage.

Experimental work was performed to investigate the impact performance of composite panels manufactured from Hercules AS4/3501-6⁸. The panels were 0.28 m long, 0.127 m wide and 0.0068 m thick, and the layup was [45/0/-45/90]_{6s}. The state of the impact damage in the panels was characterized using the time-of-flight C-scan technique. It has been determined that the shape of the impact damage is circular and the largest sublaminates at the back surface has a thickness of 4 plies. The material data are $E_1 = 140.0 \text{ GPa}$, $E_t = 8.2 \text{ GPa}$, $G = 6.2 \text{ GPa}$, and $\nu = 0.3$, and a characteristic length of zero is used in the prediction. The strength ratios obtained by prediction and those determined by tests are plotted against damage area in Fig. 3 and good correlation is demonstrated.

Figure 3. Residual strength of AS4/3501-6 [45/0/-45/90]_{6s} laminates with circular impact damage.

The effects of the orientation and the aspect ratio of damage ellipse on the residual compressive strength were investigated using the analytical model for Hexcel T800/3900-2 [45/0/-45/90]_{3s} laminates. The material data are $E_1 = 150.96 \text{ GPa}$, $E_t = 9.03 \text{ GPa}$, $G = 5.1 \text{ GPa}$, and $\nu = 0.33$. A characteristic length of 0.001 m was used in the prediction. The laminates were 0.28 m long, 0.127 m wide and 0.00564 m thick. In Fig. 4a, the strength ratio of the laminate having a two ply

sublaminates is plotted against the angle of the orientation of the elliptical impact damage with respect to the loading direction. The strength ratio is the lowest when the major axis is normal to the loading direction. In Fig. 4b, the strength ratio of the same laminate is plotted against the aspect ratio of elliptical impact damage with an area of 0.000507 m^2 . It is shown that the residual strength increases with the aspect ratio.

Figure 4. Parametric study on residual strength of T800/3900-2 [45/0/-45/90]_{6s} laminates.

4. CONCLUSIONS

An analytical model for the prediction of the compression-after-impact strength of composite laminates has been developed. The model is incorporated into a computer code DAS which can be used in PC and Unix environments for the design of composite structures. Preliminary verification has been carried out by comparing the predictive results from two test cases against published experimental data and good agreement has been obtained.

The effects of orientation and aspect ratio of the damage ellipse on the residual compressive strength were investigated using the analytical model. An increase in aspect ratio has been shown to have an

effect on improving the residual compressive strength and an increase in the orientation angle of the major axis of the elliptical impact damage with the loading direction from 0° to 90° has been found to lower the compression-after-impact strength. The lowest strength has been determined to occur when the major axis is normal to the loading direction.

Acknowledgements

This work is carried out under a Collaborative Agreement with de Havilland Inc. regarding application of composites to primary structures dated September 19, 1991 and IAR Program 3G3, Aerospace Structures, Structural Dynamics and Acoustics, Project JGT Composite Design and Analysis System.

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